
Secrets, Silence and the Fragility of Marriage: Challenges to the Family Institution in Alice Feeney's *Rock Paper Scissors*

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Abstract:

*The family as an institution has historically always served as the structural unit of social stability, emotional support, and cultural continuity. However, drastic social transformations have hugely challenged the traditional family structures. The historical perspective of family and different roles played by the individuals as a member of family has also changed drastically. Literature often reflects these changes by portraying tensions, conflicts, and psychological struggles within families in different ways. This paper examines the threats and challenges to the family institution through a literary analysis of a contemporary novel *Rock Paper Scissors* by Alice Feeney who is a contemporary British writer well known for her psychological thrillers. The novel presents a troubled marriage, usually seen nowadays easily. It depicts secrets, miscommunication, emotional distance, and psychological manipulation in the family. This novel presents the modern transformed family and the familial roles. Through great narrative techniques and detailed character development, Feeney illustrates how modern relationships are affected by mistrust, individualism, and communication breakdown. She portrays the characters in a precise way that we absorb deep down in the characters psychological condition. The study highlights how contemporary literature exposes the fragile nature of family bonds in modern society. The paper argues that Feeney's novel provides a powerful commentary on the complexities and vulnerabilities of the modern family institution.*

Keywords: *Family Institution, Marital Conflict, Modern Relationships, Secrecy.*

Introduction:

The family is traditionally regarded as the most important social institution. It is considered responsible for nurturing individuals and transmitting cultural values. But, in today's society, the structure and function of the family are changing drastically. Social norms are changing, individualism is increasing, and gender roles are transforming which have introduced new challenges to relationships in family.

Literature is known as the mirror of life, so it reflects the modern transformations by portraying the emotional and psychological complexities which are present in modern families. Contemporary fiction, mainly

psychological thrillers, frequently explore themes of marital conflict, trust, and identity in close relationships like family. The selected novel is also a psychological thriller which explores a family with troubled marriage, secrets and many more individual self-content aspects which denote that the family bonds are fragile and not true to themselves too. Novel *Rock Paper Scissors* by Alice Feeney explores these themes deeply. The story is about a married couple whose relationship is filled with secrets and unresolved tensions among themselves which they are inter-tangled in. The narrative structure and psychological depth of the novel reveals how communication

failure and hidden truths can spoil the stability of the family institution.

This paper examines the novel in the perspective of family studies and contemporary literary analysis. It focuses on how Feeney portrays the challenges faced by modern marriages or families. It also focuses on the outcomes of such vulnerabilities.

Marriage, Family and *Rock Papers Scissors*:

Right from the old times marriage has been considered the foundation of the family institution. Marriage traditionally represents mutual support, companionship and shared responsibility among the couple. But modern societies are experiencing significant changes in marital expectations and familial roles because of the development and transformed gender roles.

The industrialization, urbanization, and economic independence of individuals irrespective of their gender have altered the dynamics of marriage. Couples today often struggle to balance personal aspirations with shared responsibilities. Women are forced to manage family and career by themselves. They face the traditional harassment in the educated and modern families as well. These pressures sometimes lead to emotional distance and marital instability. It may also cause dangerous psychological changes.

In literature, the family often functions as a mirror of society. Conflicts in the families reflect broader social tensions such as shifting power dynamics, changing gender roles, failure of expectations and cultural transformation.

In *Rock Paper Scissors*, Feeney portrays a marriage that appears stable on the outside but is deeply fractured inside. The novel highlights how hidden secrets and unresolved conflicts can erode the foundation of a relationship.

The novel is about a married couple, Adam and Amelia Wright, whose relationship has

deteriorated over time. Willing to repair their marriage, they travel to a remote old chapel in the Scottish Highlands for a weekend. The holiday plan is won by Amelia for free from an anonymous online source.

The story dives through multiple perspectives and letters written by Robin former wife of Adam to him on their wedding anniversaries. Those letters gradually reveal secrets and emotional truths about their relationship which they were hiding in their relationship. The twists and the plot changes are really unexpected by the readers.

The setting intensifies the psychological tension between the characters as it is isolated and gloomy. As the story develops further the reader discovers that the couple's relationship is built on deception, misunderstandings, and hidden motives. It is revealed gradually. The truth is revealed at the end which makes readers gasp. The novel portrays the actual modern themes like deception, morality degradation and loyalty.

Through this novel, Feeney tries to explore the fragility of trust within marriage and the psychological complexities of close relationships.

Major Threats to the Family Institution in the Novel *Rock Paper Scissors*:

1. Communication Breakdown:

One of the most significant threats to the family institution portrayed in the novel is the failure of communication between spouses. Communication is very important in any relationship to sustain. It is impossible to be happy in a family without proper communication and truthfulness.

Adam suffers from face blindness (prosopagnosia), so he is unable to recognize faces. This condition symbolizes the emotional disconnect in the marriage, as Adam struggles not only to recognize people physically but also to

understand emotions. The theme of blindness both physical and psychological is depicted in this novel.

The couple rarely expresses their true feelings openly in this novel. Their relationship is marked by silence, misunderstandings, and emotional suppression. It leads to the decay of the relationships and the marriage ultimately. The couple is not true to each other. They both have secrets hidden from years.

This communication gap illustrates how emotional distance can gradually weaken the foundations of marriage and can end it slowly like a slow poison.

2. Secrets and Deception:

Secrecy plays a vital role in the deterioration of the relationship, marriage and a family ultimately. Both Adam and Amelia hide important aspects of their own lives from each other. It leads to the fall of their relationship and marriage. The truths revealed at the end of the novel make them both shocked.

The letters written by Robin on their anniversaries reveal the hidden frustrations and truths that she never communicated directly with her husband Adam. The use of anniversary letters is particularly significant. These letters function as a form of delayed communication, illustrating how unspoken emotions accumulate over time creating mistrust and emotional tension between them and it bursts out in an unimagined way for both of them.

Feeney with her novel *Rock Paper Scissors* suggests to us as readers that honesty and transparency are essential for maintaining strong family relationships. Through this novel Feeney makes us rethink the marriages led with decisive minds and dishonest individuals. It also depicts the importance of being true in a relationship. The reason for a successful relationship and a family ultimately is being true, honest, expressive and transparent. These aspects are missing in today's

modern society which is leading to failed marriages and disturbed families.

3 Psychological Manipulation:

Another challenge to the family institution depicted in the novel *Rock Paper Scissors* is psychological manipulation. Characters are engaged in subtle forms of control and deception that undermine trust. This leads to failure as an individual in a relationship and as a member of a family.

The novel gradually reveals that the couple's relationship is shaped by power struggles rather than mutual understanding. They both are engaged in keeping their secrets hidden from each other like Adam hides the truth about being in the car which hit his mother to death. Amelia hides that she was the one present at the spot with him in childhood when his mother died.

The novel uses multiple perspectives, which allow readers to understand the internal thoughts and emotions of different characters. This technique reveals how misunderstandings arise when individuals interpret the same events differently. This portrayal highlights how toxic emotional dynamics can destabilize family structures.

4. Isolation and Emotional Alienation:

The remote setting of the novel symbolizes the emotional isolation experienced by the characters. Although Adam and Amelia are physically together, they remain psychologically distant. They are not close psychologically. The cold, dark and gloomy weather symbolizes the tension among them and psychological darkness.

Modern relationships often suffer from similar forms of emotional alienation. The pressures of contemporary life, personal ambitions, traditional expectations, changing gender roles and unresolved conflicts can create barriers between partners.

Feeney uses the setting to emphasize the loneliness that can exist within marriage. Through

carefully crafted dialogue and internal monologues, the author exposes the emotional vulnerabilities of the characters.

Feeney's novel reflects broader societal concerns about trust, communication, and emotional intimacy in modern relationships. It illustrates how external pressures and internal insecurities can threaten the stability of the family institution.

At the same time, the novel encourages readers to reflect on the importance of empathy, honesty, and open communication within families.

Conclusion:

The family institution continues to evolve in response to social and cultural changes. Modern literature plays an important role in examining these transformations by portraying the complexities of intimate relationships.

Alice Feeney's *Rock Paper Scissors* provides a powerful portrayal of the challenges faced by modern relationships, marriages and families ultimately. Through themes of secrecy, communication breakdown, and psychological

conflict, the novel illustrates how fragile family relationships can become when trust, understanding and transparency are missing in a family.

By analysing the novel from a literary and sociological perspective, this paper demonstrates that contemporary fiction serves as a valuable lens through which the changing dynamics of the family institution can be understood. Ultimately, Feeney's work reminds readers that the stability of the family depends not only on social structures but also on emotional honesty and mutual understanding.

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